

The Effectiveness of Foreign Trade on Selected Macroeconomic Indicators in Iraq for the Period 2004–2023: An Empirical Study

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Abstract

This research aims to shed light on the effectiveness of foreign trade on selected macroeconomic indicators in Iraq during the period 2004–2023. To achieve this objective, the study employed a deductive approach that integrates both a theoretical descriptive method based on economic theory and a quantitative method through the use of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. This model was applied to measure the impact of foreign trade on several key macroeconomic indicators. The findings revealed that foreign trade plays a significant role in influencing macroeconomic indicators over the study period. Specifically, the highest level of effectiveness in changes to public expenditure was attributed to trade openness, which accounted for 66% of the total short-run impact. This was followed by the effectiveness of total exports at 36%, and total imports at 25%. Conversely, the highest impact on inflation rate fluctuations stemmed from total imports, which contributed 273% of the total short-run effect. This was followed by total exports, with a short-run impact of 76%, and trade openness with 62% of the total short-run effect on inflation. Based on these results, the study concludes with a set of recommendations aimed at diversifying Iraq's oil and non-oil exports and emphasizing the development of productive sectors to reduce dependency on imports, particularly consumer goods. Such measures are essential to address the structural issues facing the Iraqi economy and to achieve real growth rates and sustainable development.

Keywords: *Foreign trade, trade openness, inflation rate, government expenditure.*

JEL Classification codes: *B22, O11.*

Suggested citation: Al-Ahbabi, A.M.D., & Assaf, N.D. (2025). The Effectiveness of Foreign Trade on Selected Macroeconomic Indicators in Iraq for the Period 2004–2023: An Empirical Study. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 2(4), 15-35. DOI: 10.59324/ejm eb.2025.2(4).02

Introduction

Foreign trade represents one of the fundamental pillars that contribute to strengthening national economies, regardless of their level of development. It plays an active role in improving living standards and societal well-being by providing goods and services that cannot be produced locally or are insufficiently supplied by the domestic production apparatus. Additionally, foreign trade

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fosters economic relations among countries within a global regulatory framework that encompasses most nations, thereby playing a prominent role in achieving economic development.

As is well known, the Iraqi economy experienced a significant increase in foreign trade after 2003, following the economic liberalization that occurred with the lifting of international sanctions on the country. The surge in oil revenues led to an increase in public spending and, consequently, in national income. However, this monetary flow was not matched by a corresponding flow of goods, due to the limited flexibility of the production apparatus resulting from the dysfunction of most productive sectors and inefficiencies in others. These conditions were a natural consequence of the economic challenges that Iraq had endured over previous years. As a result, inflationary pressures emerged, fueled by imports, which inundated the local markets with goods and products that domestic producers could not compete with. Simultaneously, commodity exports remained limited, leading to a trade imbalance and a growing economic dependency on external markets.

Like many other developing countries, Iraq faces numerous macroeconomic challenges, including unemployment, inflation, the dominance of current expenditures over capital investments, and the volatility of domestic investment volumes. Furthermore, the structure of public expenditure suffers from inefficiencies in the allocation of financial resources, with a notable increase in allocations toward the operational budget at the expense of the investment budget. There is also a misallocation within expenditure components and a lack of prudence in managing investment spending, which has led to widespread waste in investment projects. All of these factors have contributed to the deterioration of productive sectors and a decline in their contribution to GDP.

Against this backdrop, as Iraq looks forward to achieving development and economic reform, it becomes imperative for policymakers to find comprehensive solutions to the country's economic problems and to adopt measures capable of realizing these objectives. This requires the implementation of a strategic reform plan in which foreign trade plays an effective role in improving the trade balance, increasing non-oil exports, and leveraging the positive aspects of trade openness such as attracting foreign investments and strengthening international economic relations. All of this would contribute to diversifying national income sources and achieving the desired level of economic performance.

During the study period, the Iraqi economy underwent significant transformations across various sectors, including the foreign trade sector. This sector was particularly affected by the prevailing political events and economic climate over the past two decades. Chief among the influencing factors was the economic and trade liberalization that followed the year 2003, leading to a near-total dependence on oil export revenues. Accompanying this shift was the weak contribution of other economic sectors, which resulted in negative economic consequences most notably, a consumerist tendency fueled primarily through imports.

Based on the above, the research problem is centered on the nature of the relationship between foreign trade and selected macroeconomic indicators in Iraq post-2003. This issue can be articulated through the following research questions:

1. Does foreign trade play an active role in generating positive changes in key macroeconomic indicators, such as the inflation rate and public expenditure?
2. Can the efficiency of Iraq's foreign trade be enhanced to make it more effective?

Research Hypothesis

To address the aforementioned questions, the following hypothesis has been formulated:

"Foreign trade with its components of exports and imports, along with trade openness plays an effective role in influencing selected macroeconomic indicators in Iraq after 2003."

Research Objectives

In order to address the research problem and test the validity of the proposed hypothesis, whether by confirmation or refutation, this study aims to achieve the following objectives:

1. To provide a theoretical and analytical presentation of the research variables namely, foreign trade and selected macroeconomic indicators and to explore the relationship between them.
2. To review the numerical evidence and statistical indicators related to the Iraqi economy during the study period, focusing on foreign trade on one hand and key macroeconomic indicators on the other.
3. To identify the functional relationship and measure the impact of the independent variables represented by the components of foreign trade on the dependent variables represented by selected macroeconomic indicators in the Iraqi economy, while also determining the causal relationship between these variables.
4. To present a set of proposals aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of foreign trade in Iraq.

Research Scope

Spatial Scope: Iraq is selected as the case study for this research.

Temporal Scope: The study covers the period from 2004 to 2023, a timeframe during which the Iraqi economy witnessed significant transformations, becoming more reliant on foreign trade and increasingly open to global markets.

Literature Review

Previous studies serve as a foundational pillar for the development of scientific research. Numerous studies have examined the effects of foreign trade on macroeconomic components, including the following:

1. Salam Hamil Brighesh (2021), “The Impact of Foreign Trade on Achieving Macroeconomic Balance in Iraq Under Economic Openness.”

This study aimed to investigate whether foreign trade, within the context of economic openness, contributes to instability or imbalance among Iraq's macroeconomic variables. It was based on the hypothesis that foreign trade positively influences certain macroeconomic indicators, thereby contributing to overall economic balance. The study concluded that increased trade openness significantly affects the volatility of Iraq's macroeconomic variables, mainly due to the limited flexibility of the productive apparatus in meeting domestic demand. Consequently, this gap is filled by the external sector, leading to higher income leakage from the national economy.

2. Michael Benarroch & Manish Pandey (2017), “The Impact of Imports and Exports on the Size and Composition of Government Expenditures.”

This study examines how government spending responds to changes in foreign trade volume and trade openness. Specifically, it explores the relationship between openness and both productive and non-productive government expenditures across 68 countries (30 low-income and 38 high-income) for the period 1972–2000. The results indicate that productive government spending tends to increase primarily with trade openness, especially as imports rise. Moreover, this relationship is more prominent in low-income countries compared to high-income ones. The authors recommend that governments increase spending in productive areas to counteract the negative impacts of greater exposure to imported goods.

The Concept and Importance of Foreign Trade

The foreign trade sector is considered one of the most vital components of the economy. Consequently, numerous economists have attempted to define foreign trade according to their perspectives. Some define it as the total volume of goods and services exchanged between countries (Sadeghi et al., 2024,108) (Krugman, 2018, p. 23). Others consider foreign trade a field within economics that applies microeconomic concepts to better understand international economic relations. It primarily involves analyzing the supply and demand of goods and services not on a local scale, but within international markets, by describing a typical pattern of economic interactions between domestic economic activities and the global economy (Suranovic, 2010, p. 8).

Moreover, foreign trade encompasses all commercial activities that facilitate the exchange of goods, services, economic resources, people, ideas, and technologies across national borders. (Al-Sabaawe et al., 2021: 1459; Jankulovski et al., 2017: 105).

Based on the above, foreign trade can be simply defined as the process of exchanging goods and services between countries, as well as between companies and individuals at the international level. More comprehensively, it may be defined as the system of goods and services relationships that together constitute the total foreign trade of all countries worldwide.

The Importance of Foreign Trade

The importance of foreign trade can be summarized as follows (Ekmekcioglu, 2011: 193):

1. Source of Foreign Currency: Foreign trade is a fundamental source of foreign exchange, which enhances a country's liquidity an essential element in economic operations, particularly in financing and investment activities.
2. Development of Economic Activities: Foreign trade contributes to the development of various economic activities whether productive, consumptive, or service-oriented by stimulating commercial movement through import and export operations.
3. Revenue Generation: Foreign trade generates financial returns that can be utilized as a source for financing development or service-oriented projects needed by the state.
4. Provision of Goods and Services: It ensures the availability of essential and luxury goods and services that a country may not be able to produce, thereby contributing to economic equilibrium.
5. Balance of Payments Adjustment: Foreign trade helps in achieving balance in the balance of payments or reducing deficits when imbalances arise. It supports equilibrium between the monetary flow and the real flow of goods and services within the economy.
6. Technology and Knowledge Transfer: It facilitates the transfer of technology between developed and developing countries and the exchange of material, human, and technological expertise.
7. Meeting Consumer Needs: Foreign trade fulfills domestic consumer demands, enhances consumer taste, and satisfies evolving preferences (Hilal, 2014, p. 107).
8. Strengthening International Relations: It reinforces existing relationships with trading partners and establishes new commercial ties with other countries and regions.

Public Expenditure

Public expenditure is defined as a sum of money disbursed from the state's financial resources through its various administrations, ministries, institutions, and agencies with the aim of satisfying public needs (Abu Hamad, 2002, p. 63). In this sense, public expenditure is characterized by three main elements that distinguish it from other types of spending (Khalaf, 2008: 90):

1. Public expenditure is a monetary amount.
2. It is issued by the state or one of its public bodies.
3. Its objective is to satisfy a public need.
4. The Economic Effects of Public Expenditure:

In most countries, public expenditure constitutes a significant share of national income due to its substantial influence on both the economic and social structures. The key effects of public spending can be summarized as follows:

1. The Impact of Public Expenditure on National Production:

Public expenditure influences production and labor force participation through its effect on the level of aggregate effective demand. This impact manifests in several forms (Gurung et al., 2023: 33):

Productive Expenditures: These are undertaken directly by the state as a "producing entity" or indirectly through subsidies to certain public or private enterprises aimed at achieving specific economic objectives.

Social Expenditures: These can take the form of direct cash transfers to households, which help raise the consumption levels of certain social groups and improve the living conditions of non-productive individuals such as the elderly and the disabled. Alternatively, they may be provided as in-kind goods and services such as healthcare, housing, and education. In both cases, such expenditures stimulate aggregate demand and, subsequently, national output.

2. The Impact of Public Expenditure on National Consumption:

The state consumes a large quantity of goods and services as part of its role in fulfilling public needs, spending funds on the operation of public facilities. This includes purchasing specific consumer goods to meet the needs of its personnel, such as food, clothing, and various equipment. In addition, the state provides essential services such as education and healthcare, which directly increase national consumption.

Furthermore, public expenditure in the form of salaries and wages one of the most important forms of government spending is primarily allocated to meet the consumption needs of income recipients. As a result, this contributes significantly to raising the overall level of national consumption (Al-Haj, 2012: 143).

Inflation

Despite the various definitions of inflation, most agree that it refers to the continuous rise in the general price level accompanied by a decline in the purchasing power of a unit of currency. To ensure precision, the following points should be considered (Ibrahim, 2024, p. 13):

1. Inflation denotes a sustained increase in the general price level, not merely a temporary or short-term rise in prices.
2. The price increase must affect all goods and services, not just a limited number of items.

Accordingly, inflation is fundamentally based on the concept of excess demand exceeding the available supply of goods in the market. When the amount of money in circulation surpasses the quantity of goods available in the economy, the value of money declines referred to as a decrease in money value or, metaphorically, currency depreciation. This, in turn, impacts individuals' incomes, as they must spend more money than before to purchase the same goods they previously bought at lower prices.

A temporary occurrence of this phenomenon is known as rising prices, but if it persists for a relatively long period (typically a year or more), it is classified as inflation (Cochrane, 2024, p. 28).

Types of Inflation

There are several criteria for classifying inflation, which vary according to the theories explaining inflation and its resulting effects:

1. Hyperinflation:

Hyperinflation refers to an extreme and rapid rise in prices, typically exceeding 50% per month and sometimes surpassing 100% annually. A historical example of hyperinflation occurred in Germany during World War I and II (Abu Ramadan, 2016, p. 16).

2. Repressed Inflation:

Also known as hidden inflation, this type occurs under strong government intervention. It represents inflation that is postponed or suppressed through government measures such as price controls, rationing, and subsidies on essential goods and services. This form is commonly seen in centrally planned economies where prices do not rise freely due to regulatory constraints. It is also referred to as controlled inflation (Duheim, 2022, p. 6).

3. Imported Inflation:

Imported inflation results from external factors, specifically when the general price level domestically increases due to rising prices of goods imported from other countries. This type is evident in economies that heavily depend on imports (Al-Sareti & Naja, 2013, p. 321).

Analysis of the Relationship Between Foreign Trade and Selected Macroeconomic Variables in Iraq (2004–2023)

Analysis of the Relationship Between Foreign Trade and Public Expenditure in Iraq (2004–2023)

Foreign trade exerts multifaceted effects on public expenditure, depending on the economic structure and the policies adopted by the state. Foreign trade can enhance the efficiency of public spending; for example, external competition may improve the efficiency of local companies, thereby reducing the need for government subsidies.

On the other hand, foreign trade can provide goods and services at relatively lower costs to the government, which in turn reduces the overall cost of public expenditure. More importantly, foreign trade contributes to increasing government revenues through customs duties and taxes on exports and imports (Planning, 2021, pp. 14–15).

Table 1 illustrates that government expenditure in Iraq has shown a fluctuating upward trend, which has become a characteristic of such spending throughout the study period. The volatility in public expenditure is mainly due to Iraq's heavy reliance on crude oil revenues, the price of which is relatively unstable on the global market. Therefore, fluctuations in these expenditures stem from fluctuations in oil revenues, given the country's policy of "spending what is collected." This approach poses a significant challenge for policymakers responsible for macroeconomic policies, especially fiscal policy in Iraq.

This relationship is further clarified in Figure 1, which shows a nearly perfect alignment between the trajectory of public expenditure (in red) and exports (in black), providing clear evidence of the impact foreign trade has on the volume of public expenditure in Iraq.

Table 1. Relationship Between Foreign Trade and Public Expenditure in Iraq (2004–2023)

Years	Exports	Imports	Trade Openness	Public Expenditure
2004	25877930	30952242	112.6	32117491.3
2005	35713515	17038940.85	110.0	26375175.1
2006	43072410.96	16899504.6	83.7	38806679.3
2007	52286433.1	7871971.354	75.1	39031232.2
2008	73527955.4	6680169.7	77.6	59403374.7
2009	48900442.4	20217192	76.7	55589721
2010	62296146.7	32688708.07	72.5	70134201
2011	194496332	58037545.3	72.6	78757667
2012	110298839.1	28587997.4	72.5	105139575
2013	104645522.5	39057185.3	66.0	119127556
2014	98539318.8	43261711.1	67.0	112192126
2015	57610951.2	48578232.7	64.7	70417515
2016	51742504.9	57353324.3	52.8	73571000
2017	70950148.3	37361218.7	57.9	75490200
2018	100684985	43804511.1	62.4	80873188.8
2019	98225336.1	24803819.7	66.5	111723523
2020	57141527	18390722.88	56.5	76082452
2021	121560002.4	20438162.8	64.8	102849470
2022	180910609.3	31990783.2	68.1	116959623
2023	151964911.8	38069032.01	76.6	142435763

Source: The table was prepared by the researchers based on various editions of the Annual Statistical Aggregates for the years 2004–2023, published by the Central Statistical Organization, Iraqi Ministry of Planning.

Figure 1. The Relationship Between Foreign Trade and Public Expenditure in Iraq for the Period (2004–2023)

Note: The figure was prepared by the researchers based on Table 1.

Analysis of the Relationship Between Foreign Trade and the Inflation Rate in Iraq for the Period (2004–2023)

Foreign trade has complex effects on inflation, which can be either positive or negative depending on several economic factors. For example, foreign trade increases competition in the domestic market, compelling local companies to lower their prices or improve product quality to maintain competitiveness. Foreign trade also enables the importation of goods and services, increasing supply in the local market, which can reduce prices, especially if demand remains constant. Since foreign trade provides consumers access to goods and services cheaper than those produced locally, it helps reduce the cost of living and contributes to controlling inflation.

Conversely, importing goods and services from countries experiencing high inflation rates can transfer inflation to the importing country known as "imported inflation" because rising prices of imported goods may lead to increased prices in the domestic market (Al-Kubaisi & Muthanna, 2018, p. 264).

Table 2 below shows that inflation rates in Iraq have generally increased since 2004, coinciding with the country's economic openness and the rise in imports due to shortages in domestic supply caused by the shutdown of most local establishments. Inflation peaked in 2006 at 53.2%, a result of deteriorating security conditions at the time. It then declined significantly in 2008 to 2.7%. Noticeable price level stability has been observed, particularly after 2013, reflecting the success of monetary authorities in maintaining exchange rate stability through currency sale windows. Consequently, inflationary effects that could have been generated by exchange rate fluctuations were mitigated (Central Bank of Iraq, 2018, p. 4).

This is clearly illustrated in Figure 2 below, where the time series of the inflation rate (in red) shows a gradual decline during the study period, coinciding with the gradual decrease of the time series.

Table 2. Relationship Between Foreign Trade and Inflation Rate in Iraq for the Period (2004–2023)

Years	Exports	Imports	Trade Openness	Inflation Rate
2004	25877930	30952242	112.6	26.8
2005	35713515	17038940.85	110.0	37
2006	43072410.96	16899504.6	83.7	53.2
2007	52286433.1	7871971.354	75.1	30.9
2008	73527955.4	6680169.7	77.6	2.7
2009	48900442.4	20217192	76.7	8.3
2010	62296146.7	32688708.07	72.5	2.5
2011	194496332	58037545.3	72.6	5.6
2012	110298839.1	28587997.4	72.5	6.05
2013	104645522.5	39057185.3	66.0	1.9
2014	98539318.8	43261711.1	67.0	2.2
2015	57610951.2	48578232.7	64.7	1.4
2016	51742504.9	57353324.3	52.8	0.4
2017	70950148.3	37361218.7	57.9	0.2
2018	100684985	43804511.1	62.4	0.4
2019	98225336.1	24803819.7	66.5	(0.1)
2020	57141527	18390722.88	56.5	0.6
2021	121560002.4	20438162.8	64.8	6.08
2022	180910609.3	31990783.2	68.1	5
2023	151964911.8	38069032.01	76.6	5.2

Note: The table was prepared by the researchers based on the Annual Statistical Aggregates (2004–2023) issued by the Central Statistical Organization.

Figure 2. The Relationship Between Foreign Trade and Local Investment in Iraq for the Period (2004–2023)

Note: The figure was prepared by the researchers based on the results from Table 2.

The trade openness indicator is shown in black, while the figure indicates a gradual increase in imports (shown in blue) during the study period. This may suggest that the inflation rate in Iraq is positively correlated with the degree of trade openness and inversely correlated with the volume of imports.

Measuring and Analyzing the Impact of Foreign Trade on Selected Macroeconomic Variables in Iraq (2004–2023)

Model One

This model estimates the effectiveness of foreign trade as an explanatory variable on public expenditure as the dependent variable. Its function and equation can be formulated as follows:

$$Y1 = F(X1, X2, X3) \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta Y1 = C + B_1 X1_{t-1} + B_2 X2_{t-1} + B_3 X3_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{q_1} \lambda_1 \Delta X1_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{q_1} \lambda_2 \Delta X2_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{q_2} \lambda_3 \Delta X3_{t-i} + \epsilon t \quad (2)$$

Model Two

This model estimates the effectiveness of foreign trade as an explanatory variable on the inflation rate as the dependent variable. Its function and equation can be formulated as follows:

$$Y2 = F(X1, X2, X3) \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta Y_2 = C + B_1 X_{1,t-1} + B_2 X_{2,t-1} + B_3 X_{3,t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^q \lambda_1 \Delta X_{1,t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{q_1} \lambda_2 \Delta X_{2,t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{q_2} \lambda_3 \Delta X_{3,t-i} + \epsilon_t \quad (4)$$

The independent variables are represented as follows: Exports X_1, Imports X_2, Trade Openness X_3.

First: Results of Unit Root Tests for Stationarity

To ensure a more accurate examination of the stationarity of the study variables, unit root tests are employed as a reliable and necessary step. These tests form the foundation for the subsequent model estimation tests. One of the most important of these tests is the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test.

1. Results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test

Table 3 presents the results of the unit root test for stationarity of the study variables in their linear form. It is clear that not all variables were stationary at their original levels, as the calculated t-value was smaller than the critical t-value at significance levels of 1% and 5%, implying acceptance of the null hypothesis $H_0: \beta = 0$, which states the presence of a unit root in the time series data. However, after first differencing the data, the variables became stationary since the calculated t-value exceeded the critical t-value at the same significance levels, leading to acceptance of the alternative hypothesis $H_1: \beta \neq 0$, indicating no unit root in the differenced data.

This implies that the data are integrated of order I(1), whether with a constant, a constant and a trend, or without either.

Table 3. Results of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test at Original Level and First Difference

UNIT ROOT TEST TABLE (ADF)						
At Level						
With Constant	Variables	X1	X2	X3	Y1	Y2
	t-Statistic	-1.9972	-2.1639	-3.7168	-1.0523	-2.1314
	Prob.	0.2874	0.2211	0.0057	0.7303	0.2332
	Result	n0	n0		n0	n0
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-2.2907	-2.3880	-2.3458	-2.2184	-1.7275
	Prob.	0.4332	0.3825	0.4044	0.4724	0.7291
	Result	n0	n0	n0	n0	n0
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	0.0256	-0.3999	-1.1067	0.9851	-0.7133
	Prob.	0.6876	0.5364	0.2414	0.9129	0.4044
	Result	n0	n0	n0	n0	n0
With Constant	Variables	d(X1)	d(X2)	d(X3)	d(Y2)	d(Y3)
	t-Statistic	-3.1885	-3.3585	-3.0725	-2.9249	-3.4480
	Prob.	0.0249	0.0157	0.0330	0.0473	0.0123
	Result					
With Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-3.1407	-3.3241	-5.1816	-2.9199	-3.6419
	Prob.	0.1052	0.0703	0.0004	0.1624	0.0330
	Result	n0			n0	
Without Constant & Trend	t-Statistic	-3.1276	-3.3636	-3.0479	-2.5623	-3.4934
	Prob.	0.0022	0.0010	0.0027	0.0110	0.0007
	Result	***	***	***	**	***

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the outputs of Eviews 10 software.

Note: The symbol (*) indicates significance at the 10% level. (**) indicates significance at the 5% level. (***) indicates significance at the 1% level.

2. Selection of the Appropriate Estimation Model for the Study Variables

After verifying the stationarity of the time series variables using graphical tests and unit root tests, it was found that the studied variables are stationary at different levels, either at the original level or after first differencing. Accordingly, it became necessary to apply the cointegration methodology through the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model to estimate the equilibrium relationship between the variables in both the short and long run. The ARDL model is considered the optimal choice for this study due to its flexibility in handling time series integrated at different orders, unlike the Engle-Granger and Johansen tests which require all time series to be integrated of the same order.

3. Preliminary Estimation of the Public Expenditure Model

Table 4 presents the preliminary estimation results of the model, where the coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.98$, indicating that the independent variables (foreign trade) explain approximately 98% of the variation in the dependent variable (public expenditure), while the remaining 2% is attributed to random factors and other changes not included in the model. Additionally, the value of the coefficient of determination is less than the Durbin-Watson statistic, confirming the absence of spurious regression among the study variables. The F-test value during the study period reached 303.452, indicating the overall significance of the estimated model.

The optimal model was selected according to the ARDL methodology, where the selected model was (1,0,4,3), based on optimal lag length criteria such as HQ, BIC, and AIC. The lag length that achieves the lowest value of these criteria is chosen. The optimal lag lengths according to the AIC test are illustrated in Figure 3.

Table 4. Preliminary Estimation Results for the Public Expenditure Model (ARDL)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Y2(-1)	1.1358	0.1210	9.3870	0.0000
Y2(-2)	-0.2375	0.1824	-1.3026	0.1974
Y2(-3)	-0.1514	0.1119	-1.3532	0.1808
X1	0.2592	0.0677	3.8314	0.0003
X1(-1)	-0.2391	0.1105	-2.1638	0.0342
X1(-2)	0.0372	0.1141	0.3259	0.7456
X1(-3)	-0.0047	0.1079	-0.0435	0.9654
X1(-4)	0.1321	0.0681	1.9402	0.0568
X2	0.0164	0.0168	0.9785	0.3315
X3	0.2939	0.2606	1.1276	0.2637
X3(-1)	-0.4068	0.2554	-1.5928	0.1161
C	1.4446	0.6712	2.1523	0.0352
R-squared	0.9812	Mean dependent var	18.1388	
Adjusted R-squared	0.9780	S.D. dependent var	0.4330	
S.E. of regression	0.0643	Akaike info criterion	-2.5069	
Sum squared resid	0.2645	Schwarz criterion	-2.1389	
Log likelihood	107.2624	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-2.3598	
F-statistic	303.4529	Durbin-Watson stat	2.1112	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the outputs of the statistical software (Eviews 10).

Figure 3. Optimal Lag Length Results According to the (AIC) Criterion

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the outputs of the statistical software (Eviews 10).

4. Results of the Bounds Test for Cointegration

To verify the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship between the independent variables (foreign trade tools) and the dependent variable (public expenditure), the F-statistic was used through the bounds test. Table 5 presents the results of the cointegration test for the public expenditure model using the bounds test within the ARDL methodology framework. The calculated F-value is compared with critical values at different significance levels to determine whether a long-run relationship exists among the variables under study.

Table 5. Results of the Cointegration Test for the Public Expenditure ARDL Model

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	6.188825	3
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.72	3.77
5%	3.23	4.35
2.5%	3.69	4.89
1%	4.29	5.61

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the outputs of the statistical software (Eviews 10).

The results show that the calculated F-statistic value reached 6.188, which is higher than the critical values for both the upper and lower bounds at significance levels of 1%, 5%, 10%, and 25%. Accordingly, the null hypothesis (H_0), which states that there is no long-run equilibrium relationship among the study variables, is rejected, while the alternative hypothesis (H_1), confirming the existence of a cointegration relationship among the variables during the study period, is accepted. This indicates the presence of a long-run equilibrium relationship directed from the set of explanatory variables toward the dependent variable (public expenditure), thereby supporting

the research hypothesis. Consequently, it becomes necessary to estimate the short-run and long-run responses as well as the Error Correction Model (ECM) parameter to measure the speed of adjustment toward long-run equilibrium.

5. Results of Estimating the Error Correction Parameter and Short- and Long-Run Coefficients

After performing the bounds test (cointegration test) and confirming the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship between the explanatory variables (foreign trade components) and the dependent variable (public expenditure), it is necessary to estimate the short-run and long-run coefficients along with the error correction parameter (ECM) of the estimated model.

Table 6 shows that the error correction coefficient satisfies both negativity and statistical significance conditions at a significance level less than 1%, indicating that 25.3% of short-run errors are automatically corrected over time to achieve long-run equilibrium. Thus, public expenditure requires about ten months to reach its long-run equilibrium value, reflected in the reduction of unproductive public expenditure in the future, indicating a relatively slow response.

Additionally, the estimates of the short-run coefficients show strong consistency in both sign and significance level with the long-run coefficients, despite some relative variation in the estimated values.

Table 6 presents the results of estimating the long- and short-run responses according to the ARDL model, aimed at analyzing the effectiveness of foreign trade and its impact on macroeconomic indicators in Iraq during the period (2004–2023).

Table 6. Results of Short- and Long-Run Coefficients and Error Correction Parameter for the Public Expenditure Model

Short-run Estimates and Error Correction Parameter				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(Y2(-1))	0.3889	0.1081	3.5967	0.0006
D(Y2(-2))	0.1514	0.1119	1.3532	0.1808
D(X1)	0.2592	0.0677	3.8314	0.0003
D(X1(-1))	-0.0372	0.1141	-0.3259	0.7456
D(X1(-2))	0.0047	0.1079	0.0435	0.9654
D(X1(-3))	-0.1321	0.0681	-1.9402	0.0568
D(X2)	0.0164	0.0168	0.9785	0.3315
D(X3)	-0.2939	0.2606	-1.1276	0.2637
CointEq(-1)	-0.2531	0.0550	-4.6011	0.0000
Cointeq = Y2 - (0.7297X1 + 0.0649X2 -0.4460X3 + 5.7069)				
Long-run Estimates				
X1	0.7297	0.0940	7.7627	0.0000
X2	0.0649	0.0628	1.0336	0.0052
X3	-0.4460	0.2274	-1.9611	0.0542
C	5.7069	2.1186	2.6937	0.0090

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the outputs of the statistical software (Eviews 10).

Evaluation of the Estimated Model's Quality from an Economic Perspective

The results shown in Table 6, which measure the relationship between foreign trade components and public expenditure in Iraq during the period (2004–2023) according to the ARDL model, are as follows:

- a) The estimated coefficient for the total exports variable (X1) indicates a positive and statistically significant relationship between total exports and public expenditure in both the short and long run. The short-run coefficient value is 0.259, meaning that a 1% increase in total exports leads to a 0.259% increase in public expenditure. Meanwhile, the long-run coefficient is 0.729, indicating that a 1% increase in total exports results in a 0.729% increase in public expenditure. This aligns with economic theory, supports the research hypothesis, and reflects the reality of the Iraqi economy.
- b) The estimated coefficient for total imports (X2) also shows a positive and significant relationship with public expenditure in both short and long run. The short-run coefficient is 0.016, meaning a 1% increase in total imports leads to a 0.016% increase in public expenditure, while the long-run coefficient is 0.064, indicating a 0.064% increase in public expenditure for every 1% increase in total imports. This result is consistent with economic theory, the research hypothesis, and the economic conditions in Iraq.
- c) The estimated coefficient for trade openness (X3) shows a negative and statistically significant relationship with public expenditure in both short and long run. The short-run coefficient is –0.293, meaning a 1% increase in trade openness in Iraq leads to a 0.293% decrease in public expenditure. The long-run coefficient is –0.446, indicating that a 1% increase in trade openness causes a 0.446% decrease in public expenditure. This is consistent with economic theory, the research hypothesis, and the Iraqi economic context.

Evaluation of the Estimated Model's Quality from a Statistical Perspective

1. Autocorrelation Test for the Public Expenditure Model

Table 7 presents the results of the autocorrelation test using the Breusch-Godfrey Lagrange Multiplier test (BGLM), which is considered the most accurate for detecting autocorrelation in time series data of a random variable. The test results indicate that the model does not suffer from serial autocorrelation. The p-values for both the F-test and the Chi-square test exceed the 5% significance level, with the p-value for the F-statistic at 0.2789 and the Chi-square statistic at 0.1504. This supports the acceptance of the null hypothesis, indicating that the estimated public expenditure model is free from serial autocorrelation problems.

Table 7. Results of the Autocorrelation (LM) Test for Public Expenditure

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	2.645917	Prob. F(2 ,62)	0.2789
ObsR-squared	5.976645	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.1504

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on outputs from the statistical software (Eviews 10).

2. Test for Homoscedasticity Stability of Variance for the Public Expenditure Model

Table 8 presents the results of the variance homoscedasticity test, indicating that the public expenditure model does not suffer from heteroscedasticity issues. The calculated F-statistic value was 1.635 with a p-value of 0.205, which supports the acceptance of the null hypothesis stating that the variance of the random error term in the estimated model is stable, and there is no heteroscedasticity problem.

Table 8. The Results of the Heteroscedasticity Test (ARCH) for the Public Expenditure Model

Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH			
F-statistic	1.635208	Prob. F(1, 73)	0.2050
ObsR-squared	1.643200	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.1999

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on outputs from the statistical software (Eviews 10).

Results of Measuring the Effectiveness of Foreign Trade and Its Impact on Local Investment in Iraq for the Period (2004-2023)

1. Preliminary Estimation of the Inflation Rate Model (ARDL)

Table 9 shows the preliminary estimation results of the model, where the coefficient of determination (R^2) reached 0.96, indicating that the independent variables (foreign trade) explain about 96% of the variation in the dependent variable (inflation rate), while the remaining 4% is attributed to random factors.

Table 9. Preliminary Estimation Results for the Inflation Rate Model (ARDL)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Y4(-1)	1.2747	0.1290	9.8800	0.0000
Y4(-2)	-0.3247	0.1859	-1.7461	0.0867
Y4(-3)	-0.0592	0.1759	-0.3365	0.7378
Y4(-4)	-0.1436	0.1089	-1.3186	0.1931
X1	-0.6617	0.3118	-2.1222	0.0386
X1(-1)	1.5810	0.5118	3.0895	0.0032
X1(-2)	-0.7000	0.2936	-2.3843	0.0208
X2	1.0999	0.3367	3.2668	0.0019
X2(-1)	-2.0541	0.5508	-3.7291	0.0005
X2(-2)	0.8524	0.3041	2.8027	0.0071
X3	4.8224	1.5384	3.1347	0.0028
X3(-1)	-7.5116	2.6674	-2.8161	0.0069
X3(-2)	2.8606	2.3308	1.2273	0.2252
X3(-3)	-0.5462	2.1124	-0.2586	0.7970
X3(-4)	2.3474	1.3213	1.7765	0.0815
C	-10.3680	2.9003	-3.5748	0.0008
R-squared	0.9805	Mean dependent var		1.2913
Adjusted R-squared	0.9749	S.D. dependent var		1.5345
S.E. of regression	0.2433	Akaike info criterion		0.2136
Sum squared resid	3.0791	Schwarz criterion		0.7358
Log likelihood	8.7374	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.4205
F-statistic	174.1601	Durbin-Watson stat		2.2403
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000			

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on outputs from the statistical software (Eviews 10).

The other variations not included in the model are also reflected. The value of the coefficient of determination (R^2) was less than the value of the Durbin-Watson statistic, confirming the absence of spurious regression among the research variables. The F-test value during the study period reached 174.160, indicating the overall significance of the estimated model. The optimal model was selected according to the ARDL methodology, with the specified model being (4, 2, 2, 4), based on criteria for selecting optimal lag lengths such as HQ, BIC, and AIC. The optimal lag lengths according to the AIC test are illustrated in Chart (4).

Figure 4. Optimal Lag Selection Results According to the AIC Criterion

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the outputs of the statistical software (Eviews 10).

2. Bounds Test Results for Cointegration

To verify the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship between the independent variables (foreign trade instruments) and the dependent variable (inflation rate), the F-statistic was used through the bounds testing approach. Table 10 presents the results of the bounds test for the inflation rate model using the ARDL methodology, where the calculated F-value is compared with the critical values at different significance levels to determine whether a long-term equilibrium relationship exists among the variables under investigation.

Table 10. Bounds Test Results for the ARDL Model of the Inflation Rate

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	5.923897	3
Critical Value Bounds		
Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.72	3.77
5%	3.23	4.35
2.5%	3.69	4.89
1%	4.29	5.61

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the outputs of the statistical software (Eviews 10).

The results showed that the calculated F-statistic value was (5.923), which is higher than its critical values for both the lower and upper bounds at significance levels of 1%, 5%, 10%, and 25%. Accordingly, the null hypothesis (H0), which states that there is no long-run equilibrium relationship among the study variables, is rejected, while the alternative hypothesis (H1), which confirms the existence of a cointegrating relationship among the variables during the study period, is accepted. This indicates the presence of a long-run equilibrium relationship from the set of explanatory variables (foreign trade instruments) to the dependent variable (inflation rate), which supports the research hypothesis. Therefore, it becomes necessary to estimate the short- and long-run responses in addition to estimating the error correction term (ECM) to measure the speed of adjustment toward long-run equilibrium.

3. Results of the Error Correction Term and the Short- and Long-Run Coefficients

After conducting the bounds test (cointegration) and confirming the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship between the explanatory variables (foreign trade instruments) and the dependent variable (inflation rate), it became necessary to estimate the short- and long-run coefficients along with the error correction term (ECM) of the estimated model. Table 11 shows that the error correction term satisfies the conditions of negativity and statistical significance at a significance level of less than 1%, indicating that 0.252 of the short-run disequilibrium is corrected automatically over time to restore long-run equilibrium. Accordingly, the inflation rate requires approximately ten months to return to its long-run equilibrium value, represented by a future reduction in inflation rates, which reflects a relatively slow response. In addition, the estimated short-run coefficients showed strong consistency in sign and level of significance with the long-run coefficients, despite some relative variation in the estimated values. Table 11 presents the estimated short- and long-run responses based on the ARDL model, aiming to analyze the effectiveness of foreign trade and its impact on macroeconomic indicators in Iraq during the period (2004–2023).

Table 11. Short- and Long-Run Coefficients and Error Correction Term Estimates for the Inflation Model

Short-Run Coefficients and Error Correction Term				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(Y4(-1))	0.5274	0.1108	4.7591	0.0000
D(Y4(-2))	0.2028	0.1147	1.7673	0.0830
D(Y4(-3))	0.1436	0.1089	1.3186	0.1931
D(X1)	0.6617	0.3118	2.1222	0.0386
D(X1(-1))	0.7000	0.2936	2.3843	0.0208
D(X2)	1.0999	0.3367	3.2668	0.0019
D(X2(-1))	-0.8524	0.3041	-2.8027	0.0071
D(X3)	4.8224	1.5384	3.1347	0.0028
D(X3(-1))	-2.8606	2.3308	-1.2273	0.2252
D(X3(-2))	0.5462	2.1124	0.2586	0.7970
D(X3(-3))	-2.3474	1.3213	-1.7765	0.0815
CointEq(-1)	-0.2527	0.0672	-3.7605	0.0004
$Cointeq = Y4 - (0.8681X1 - 0.4029X2 + 7.8063X3 - 41.0290)$				
Long-Run Coefficients				
X1	0.8681	0.3403	2.5511	0.0137
X2	0.4029	0.3092	1.3029	0.0183
X3	7.8063	1.1229	6.9517	0.0000
C	-41.0290	9.5346	-4.3032	0.0001

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the outputs of the statistical program (Eviews 10).

Evaluation of the Estimated Model from an Econometric Perspective

After estimating the parameters of the econometric model for both short- and long-term relationships and confirming its quality and suitability for measuring the effectiveness of foreign trade and its impact on macroeconomic indicators in Iraq as well as its freedom from econometric issues there arises the need to conduct diagnostic tests as follows:

1. Autocorrelation Test for the Inflation Rate Model

Table 12 presents the results of the autocorrelation test using the Breusch-Godfrey Lagrange Multiplier (BGLM) test, which is considered the most accurate for detecting autocorrelation in time series data of the stochastic error term. The test results indicate that the model does not suffer from autocorrelation, as the p-values associated with the F-statistic and Chi-square statistic exceed

the 5% significance level. The p-value of the F-statistic was 0.2333, while the p-value of the Chi-square statistic was 0.1312, supporting the acceptance of the null hypothesis that the estimated inflation model is free from serial autocorrelation.

Table 12. LM Test Results for Autocorrelation – Local Investment Model

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test			
F-statistic	1.473525	Prob. F(3 ,49)	0.2333
ObsR-squared	5.627030	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.1312

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the outputs of the statistical software (Eviews 10).

2. Heteroskedasticity Test for the Local Investment Model

Table 13 presents the results of the heteroskedasticity test, indicating that the inflation rate model does not suffer from a heteroskedasticity problem. The calculated F-statistic value was 0.262 with a corresponding probability level of 0.610, which supports the acceptance of the null hypothesis stating that the variance of the error term in the estimated model is stable. Therefore, there is no evidence of heteroskedasticity in the model.

Table 13. ARCH Test Results for Heteroskedasticity – Inflation Rate Model

Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH			
F-statistic	0.262537	Prob. F(1 ,64)	0.6101
ObsR-squared	0.269635	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.6036

Source: Prepared by the researchers based on the outputs of the statistical software (Eviews 10).

Conclusions

The study reached a set of theoretical and practical conclusions, as follows:

Theoretical and Analytical Conclusions

1. Crude oil exports hold the highest relative importance among all Iraqi exports, with a contribution rate exceeding 90% during the study period. This reflects the monostructure of Iraq's export composition, making the Iraqi economy highly sensitive to global oil price shocks.
2. Iraq witnessed a continuous increase in the volume of imports, particularly after the economic liberalization following 2003. Notably, the volume of imported petroleum products rose significantly, especially in the latter years of the study period.
3. The Iraqi trade balance suffers from qualitative distortions due to the nature of exported goods. Although the trade balance recorded surpluses during the study period, once crude oil exports are excluded, a persistent deficit becomes evident throughout the entire period.
4. The Iraqi economy was exposed to violent inflationary waves, particularly in the early years of the study period. A relatively stable inflation rate was not achieved until after 2012, reflecting the monetary authority's success in stabilizing the exchange rate.
5. Public expenditures in Iraq are characterized by a volatile upward trend, which became a dominant feature of both current and investment expenditures during the study period. This volatility is likely due to the absence of a long-term fiscal strategy capable of channeling financial resources toward productive activities. The fluctuations in public expenditures stem from the fact that government spending in Iraq is almost entirely dependent on crude oil revenues.

Applied Conclusions

1. There is a positive and significant relationship between total exports and public expenditure in both the short and long term. This is consistent with economic theory, the research hypothesis, and the reality of the Iraqi economy.
2. There is a positive and significant relationship between total imports and public expenditure in Iraq in both the short and long term. This aligns with economic theory, the research hypothesis, and the reality of the Iraqi economy.
3. There is a negative and significant but weak relationship between trade openness and public expenditure in both the short and long term. This is consistent with economic theory, the research hypothesis, and the reality of the Iraqi economy.
4. There is a positive and significant relationship between total exports and the inflation rate in Iraq in both the short and long term. This is consistent with economic theory, the research hypothesis, and the reality of the Iraqi economy.
5. There is a positive and significant relationship between total imports and the inflation rate in Iraq in both the short and long term. This is consistent with economic theory, the research hypothesis, and the reality of the Iraqi economy.
6. There is a positive and significant relationship between trade openness and the inflation rate in Iraq in both the short and long term. This does not align with economic theory or the research hypothesis, but it reflects the reality of the Iraqi economy.

Recommendations

In light of the previous conclusions, the study proposes the following recommendations:

1. Leverage Iraq's comparative advantages and utilize them to diversify the economic base in order to overcome the rentier nature of the oil-dependent economy. This can be achieved by channeling oil-generated revenues toward the activation of other sectors such as agriculture, tourism especially religious tourism and manufacturing industries, in addition to developing infrastructure, which represents the foundational base for economic activities and sectors.
2. Promote export diversification by establishing high-value production industries targeted for export, and diversifying oil exports to include refined products alongside crude oil. This can be done through the construction of new refineries and the modernization of existing ones, which would play a vital role in revitalizing the trade balance, at least in the long term.
3. Create a favorable investment climate to attract foreign investments by ensuring political and security stability, and offering incentives to investment firms to engage in projects currently beyond the capacity of the national economy. It is also recommended to empower local governments with legislative authority to enact investment laws suited to their local conditions, thereby supporting the development of sectors in which each city has a comparative advantage.
4. Empower the private sector and enable its contribution to economic activity by providing necessary resources and a conducive environment through the enactment of laws and issuance of regulations similar to those in developed countries. Additionally, offering incentives and exemptions would reassure both local and foreign investors and position the private sector as a vital partner to the public sector in the process of economic diversification.
5. Enhance the role of manufacturing industries involved in export-oriented activities by allocating land for industrial projects based on urban planning in each city. Free industrial zones can also be

established in border areas, with the provision of necessary technical infrastructure and security protections.

6. Adopt a trade policy that protects domestic production by enforcing a comprehensive customs tariff law to control border crossings and implementing anti-dumping regulations. These measures would help strengthen local production and increase the competitiveness of locally available goods, ultimately reducing economic dependency and exposure to foreign markets.

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